

Leveraging Literary Adaptations in EFL Classroom: Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of English Teachers

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Abstract. Literature is a rich repository of historical and cultural treasures, offering a wealth of knowledge and insights. Literary adaptations have emerged combining literature with media forms like films, captivating students' attention and boosting engagement. However, in the context of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom, students may still encounter setbacks. Through a qualitative phenomenological study, the researcher explored the experiences, strategies, and insights of English teachers pertaining to leveraging literary adaptation in an EFL classroom. The participants were ten (10) English teachers from different schools within Cluster 8 of Davao City. From the findings, unique narratives were gathered about the experiences, strategies, and insights of the teachers. Three themes emerged as experiences of English teachers: technological disruptions, time constraints, and diverse learning needs of students. Meanwhile, for strategies, three themes have been unfurled: introductory engagement activities, scaffolding and support, and task-based learning. For the insights, there were also three themes: increased student participation, language development, and provision of pedagogical support. The study showcases teachers' dedication to crafting enriching learning experiences that foster students' literary appreciation and comprehension, while nurturing a deeper understanding of literary pieces. The findings of this study seem to lead to the conclusion to the experiences of English teachers leveraging literary adaptations face several challenges.

KEY WORDS

1. Literary adaptation 2. pre-reading 3. post-reading

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1. Introduction

The combination of literature and cinema has resulted in literary adaptations, a compelling area of study within the context of EFL (English as a Foreign Language) instruction. These adaptations are key in addressing the issue regarding the decline of interest in reading. This study focuses on EFL students who often exhibit limited critical reading literacy. Traditionally, printed literary texts can sometimes disengage learners, hence leading educators to seek materials that make the study of literature both accessible and enjoyable, ensuring a more stimulating learning environment. Globally, several authors have highlighted several hurdles in employing literary adaptations in EFL classrooms. Many literary works feature advanced vocabulary, complex sentence structures, and cultural references that may overwhelm EFL learners, making the adaptation process crucial for accessibility. Additionally, teachers often find it challenging to preserve the integrity of the original text while creating a literary adaptation. This can lead

to oversimplification, which risks losing the essence of literary work. Despite the struggles, there is a silver lining in employing literary adaptations. It contributed to memorizing and discovering some of the British cultural aspects of that era. Therefore, opting for a cinematic milieu in a literature classroom can have dual aims: educating and entertaining, raising students' visual awareness through readings of adaptations by concertizing what is written. In addition, it indicated that teachers perceive literature as a way to enhance students' creativity and collaboration. However, these benefits are sometimes limited by resource accessibility, particularly in remote areas where teachers face challenges in accessing high-quality reading materials and training workshops. Moreover, Filipino educators have explored ways to adapt comparative literature teaching to online platforms, emphasizing the importance of technology in enhancing students' engagement with texts. The availability of digital versions of literary works allows students to analyze and interpret texts from diverse perspectives. In addition, literature's role in fostering intercultural understanding and addressing language proficiency issues has been a central theme in Philippine studies. By using relatable local and international texts, educators aim to bridge cultural and linguistic gaps. The challenges include difficulty in dealing with vocabulary words, failure in deepening literacy in text discussion, and language barriers in text discussion. The challenges hindered learners from learning and appreciating literary texts. However, current literature often emphasizes advanced learners, neglecting the needs of beginner and intermediate EFL students. Given the problems highlighted, this study is considered a timely endeavor. It intends to inform various sectors of the academic community, including educational leaders, school administrators, teachers, students, other stakeholders, and future researchers. This research will inspire guidance and support, potentially leading to programs that better integrate literary adaptations into language classes. This is significant for developing students' critical thinking skills and fostering a deeper understanding of language and culture, ultimately making learning more engaging and meaningful.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This phenomenological study explored and analyzed the experiences and coping mechanisms employed by secondary English teachers from Davao City in leveraging literary adaptations in an English as a Foreign Language classroom. I hope that the study provided useful insights into the coping mechanisms used by teachers for the enhancement of students' understanding of literary pieces. Ultimately, I strived that the study helped increase my understanding of how to effectively utilize literary strategies as an English teacher in order to help my students grow and flourish as individuals, and to cater to their needs. The central objective of this data collection revolved around capturing the real-life experiences of secondary English school teachers as they utilize coping mechanisms for employing literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. The outcomes of this phenomenological study provided me with a deeper understanding of how teaching is a transformative profession and how teachers can help in honing important facets and skills necessary for growth. Furthermore, I assessed the efficacy of these coping mechanisms in elevating the understanding of the students. The valuable insights obtained from this study possess the potential to exert a positive influence on various aspects of inclusive education and teaching, professional development initiatives, and educational policies aimed at cultivating empowering and supportive learning environments within classrooms.

1.2. Research Questions—This study explored the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations to enhance student's understanding

of literary texts in an English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom. The research is carried out with the purpose of addressing the following inquiries:

- (1) What are the lived experiences of secondary English teachers in utilizing literary adaptations in an EFL classroom?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of secondary English teachers for employing literary adaptations in an EFL classroom?
- (3) What insights can be formulated from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were described operationally. English as a Foreign Language This refers to the term that describes the study of English by non-native speakers in countries where English is not the dominant language (Nordquist, 2020). In the context of this study, English as a Foreign Language (EFL) will be defined as a term used for the

study of English by non-native English speakers, which in this case are the students.

Literary Adaptations This refers to the term used when a literary work, such as a poem or novel, is made into a new genre, such as a film or musical (Poem Analysis, 2020). In the context of this study, the literary adaptations refer the switch or change of media used in discussing a literary piece.

1.4. Theoretical Lens—The theoretical underpinning of this study was anchored on Linda Hutcheon's *A Theory of Adaptation* (2006, as cited from Adumati, 2024). The theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding adaptations as both a process and a product. Hutcheon argues that adaptations are not mere copies of original works but creative transformations that reinterpret a story across different mediums, genres, or cultural contexts. She emphasizes that adaptations can be autonomous works while maintaining a connection to their source material, offering new perspectives and experiences. Integrating it to the study's context, in EFL classrooms, this theory supports the use of adaptations like films, graphic novels, or simplified texts to make literature more accessible. Students can analyze how adaptations modify themes, language, or settings, which help develop their critical thinking and comparative analysis skills. It can also be used to make literature more accessible and engaging for students. The study was further reinforced by the Reader-Response Theory, introduced by Louise Rosenblatt (1978, Mart, 2019) emphasizes the active

role of the reader in creating meaning through their interaction with a text. Rather than focusing solely on the author's intent or the text's structure. This theory emphasizes the influence of personal experiences, emotions, and cultural backgrounds on a reader's understanding. It is especially relevant in EFL classrooms when using literary adaptations like films, graphic novels, or audio-visual materials. As applied in the context of this study, Reader-Response Theory encourages students to integrate personal reflection with critical analysis. Furthermore, it improves language skills by providing opportunities for vocabulary building, critical discussion, and narrative comprehension in the target language. It also fosters the students' awareness, empathy, and a deeper appreciation for literature's universal themes. Hence, this theory was my guide in analyzing the various coping mechanisms of teachers in employing literary adaptations in their classes to enhance students' understanding of the literary piece. To sum up, the Theory of Adaption and the Reader-Response theory are suited to use in the study as they shed light on the different aspects of literary analysis

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

from the students' end. The former highlights how students can improve their critical thinking and comparative analysis of the literary skills they are learning about. Meanwhile, the latter calls for a more personal and in-depth reflection

from the students. These two theories will guide the researcher in understanding the intricacies of leveraging literary adaptation in an EFL classroom through the lenses of English teachers.

2. Methodology

This chapter effectively addresses the specific objectives of the study by outlining the systematic procedures and methodologies used in phenomenological research. It also explains the selected research design and the roles I played as the researcher throughout the study's implementation. Moreover, it offers thorough insights into the research subjects, clarifying their procedures and selection standards. The chapter concludes by exploring the techniques used for data collection, analysis, and strategies used to uphold ethical standards during the research.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—A study's philosophical and qualitative presumptions are vital in steering the investigation. Four fundamental assumptions form the bedrock for comprehending qualitative research: ontological, epistemological, axiological, and methodological. These assumptions establish the groundwork for the research design and inform the researcher's approach to the study. A paradigm is a broad framework or

perspective that guides and shapes how researchers approach their studies, formulate research questions, gather data, analyze findings, and interpret results. It encompasses a set of beliefs, assumptions, methodologies, and theoretical foundations that influence how researchers conceptualize and conduct their research (Zukauskas et al., 2018). In this research, the paradigm guided the choice of methodology, methods, and techniques, shaping the overall

research process and ensuring coherence in the study. **Ontology** This section of the study focuses on the relationship between the problem and reality. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), ontology can be defined as the study of the nature of reality. I asserted that the research participants' perceptions of reality are varied and subjective. This study acknowledges the complex, multifaceted nature of reality as experienced by secondary English teachers. Their lived experiences, as they navigate the challenges of leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom, reveal the intricate web of meanings and interpretations that underpin their professional existence. Through thematic analysis, this research seeks to uncover the underlying ontological assumptions that shape secondary English teachers' understanding of their role, their students, and the context in which they teach. By examining the teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms, this study aims to illuminate the fundamental nature of reality as it relates to teaching, learning, and the employment of literary adaptations in an EFL context. **Epistemology** Epistemology deals with the nature of knowledge and the relationship between the knower and the known. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), I made an effort to reduce the gap between them and the participants based on the epistemological premise. By engaging directly with the participants, I became an "insider," facilitating a more authentic and nuanced collection of data. This epistemological stance recognizes that knowledge is socially constructed, context-dependent, and inherently subjective. By engaging in deep, experiential data collection, I sought to uncover the English teachers' perspective, revealing the complex, nuanced, and contextualized nature of their challenges and coping mechanisms in leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. **Axiology** It concerns the influence and importance of my values in this study. According to Creswell and Poth (2018), acknowledging and openly

discussing the values that shape the study is crucial. The values which influence how data are interpreted and presented are explicitly acknowledged in the research process. This study is grounded in a deep respect for the inherent value and dignity of each participant's narrative. I am committed to upholding the highest ethical standards, ensuring that the challenges and coping mechanisms of secondary English teachers are treated with sensitivity, integrity, and transparency. By prioritizing the values of trust, respect, and reciprocity, this research aims to co-create a safe and empathetic space for participants to share their stories regarding the employment of literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. This axiological stance recognizes the intrinsic worth and autonomy of each participant, acknowledging that their narratives are precious, personal, and deserving of careful consideration. **Methodology** According to Crotty (2020), this is "the strategy, plan of action, process, or design lying behind the choice and use of particular methods and linking the choice and use of the methods to the desired outcomes." Its objectives are to explain, assess, and defend procedures. This qualitative study employs an in-depth, phenomenological approach to explore the challenges and coping mechanisms of secondary English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations. A qualitative methodology is chosen for its ability to capture the richness, complexity, and nuance of participants' experiences. Specifically, this study utilizes in-depth interviews as the primary data collection technique. This approach enables a detailed, contextualized, and empathetic examination of participants' narratives, allowing for a deeper understanding of their challenges and coping mechanisms. **Rhetoric** In research, rhetoric is the skillful and convincing use of language, communication coping mechanisms, and presentation tactics to effectively communicate concepts, claims, and conclusions in order to sway the audience's opinion and comprehend

sion of the study (Beqiri, 2018). This study employed a narrative approach that not only respects the voices of the participants but also presents the findings in a clear, compelling, and accessible manner. Through the strategic use of language, I established a rhetorical connection with the audience, fostering empathy and understanding of the participants' challenges and

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—Using a phenomenological research methodology, my goal was to explore the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations to enhance students' understanding of literary pieces within Cluster 8 of Davao City. My objective was to gather information about their experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights in relation to the phenomenon I was studying. Utilizing phenomenology as my guiding qualitative framework, I sought to uncover the essence and significance of the roles played by these individuals, emphasizing their unique viewpoints and the intricate details of their experiences. I supported a level of investigation that goes beyond cursory observations. My research aims to investigate the experiences and coping mechanisms of participants in relation to the phenomenon. I emphasized the significance of understand-

2.3. Design and Procedure—Determining the precise approach used in a study is crucial in order to customize the best research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach to the study's objectives. I used a qualitative research design in this investigation. Hammersley (2013, cited in Aspers and Corte, 2019) states that studies characterized by verbal rather than statistical analysis are appropriate for qualitative research. Since I studied the lived experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of secondary English teachers in leveraging literary adapta-

coping mechanisms in regarding literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. I ensured that the participants' stories are conveyed with accuracy, sensitivity, and depth. This approach enables the research to resonate with its intended audience, facilitating a deeper understanding of the findings and their implications.

ing the complexities of human experience in light of the various perspectives that are shaped by unique contexts, backgrounds, and personal histories (Neubauer et al., 2019). To uncover the intricate and multifaceted nature of challenges faced by secondary English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom, my study employs a qualitative approach that prioritizes depth and contextual richness. Specifically, I utilized in-depth interviews and reflective dialogues to gather nuanced and detailed accounts from participants. Through a phenomenological lens, I analyzed participants' narratives to identify the essence of their experiences, gaining insight into their perceptions, thoughts, and feelings. This approach enables me to capture the complexities and subtleties of the teachers' experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights in leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom.

tions in an EFL classroom, the qualitative design was the most appropriate. This means that rather than establishing or refuting theories, I described and elaborated on this phenomenon. There are, however, specialized methods used in qualitative research, including grounded theory, narrative, case studies, phenomenology, and ethnography. Using a qualitative phenomenological research design, I explored the lived experiences of the participants in this particular setting. I selected this approach because, according to Asper's (2009, cited in Aspers and

Corte, 2019) work, the scientific side of phenomenological research focuses on communicating the viewpoints of the subjects and the importance of their experiences, then applying scientific concepts to analyze these perspectives. Furthermore, according to Creswell and Poth (2018), a phenomenological study is a method of inquiry that describes the complex and collective experiences of the participants with respect to a particular phenomenon. A key idea in phe-

nomenology is to reduce one's interpretations of a particular phenomenon to a description that can be applied to all situations. Therefore, my goal was to identify a phenomenon that revolves around the participants' experience of leveraging literary adaptations in EFL classroom. I collected information from people who have direct experience with this phenomenon in order to create detailed and accurate descriptions.

2.4. Research Participants—Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most or all perceptions. Obtaining most or all perceptions leads to the attainment of saturation. Saturation occurs when adding more participants to the study does not result in additional perspectives or information. Glaser and Strauss (2017) as cited in Hennink and Kaiser (2022) recommend the concept of saturation for achieving an appropriate sample size in qualitative studies. For phenomenological studies, Creswell and Poth (2018) recommends 5 to twenty-five. According to Subedi (2021), larger samples in qualitative studies hinder an in-depth exploration of the study phenomenon. There are no specific rules when determining the appropriate sample size in qualitative research. Qualitative sample size may best be determined by the time allotted, resources available, and study objectives (Patton, 2002 as cited in Mullet, 2018). With this, the participants of this study were ten (10) English teachers from five (5) different schools in Davao City within cluster 8. These schools are the following: Lacson In-

tegrated School, Subasta National High School, Sirib National High School, Baon Aguan National High School, and Simon Lada National High School. To gather a more diverse and in-depth understanding of the experiences and coping mechanisms of English teachers regarding literary adaptations in an EFL classroom, participants were selected from each school. This selection process ensures that the study captures a broad range of perspectives allowing for a more comprehensive examination of developing students' understanding of literary pieces. The participants were chosen based on the following criteria: they must be teaching in one of the five schools in Davao City, they must be teachers for more than 3 years, they must be English teachers, employ literary adaptations, and be willing to participate in the study. I utilized the purposive sampling design so that the participants are chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study (Creswell Poth, 2018). It is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996 as cited in Vasileiou et al., 2018).

2.5. Ethical Considerations—Ethical considerations are crucial because they relate to the moral principles and guidelines that govern my conduct as a researcher. These principles ensure

that I carried out my investigations responsibly, treating participants with respect and striving to generate reliable and precise information. To protect participants, maintain scientific integrity,

and foster trust within the research community, I adhere to established ethical standards in my research practices (Resnik, 2020).

Social value This concerns the potential benefits and favorable outcomes that research can bring to society, like addressing problems or improving people's quality of life. This study recognizes its societal value by addressing a critical need in education: leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. By investigating effective strategies for improving these programs, this research has the potential to create a positive impact on the broader community. The findings of this study can inform evidence-based practices, ultimately benefiting students, educators, and schools. By elevating students' problem-solving skills, this research can contribute to the development of skilled competent, and equipped students to engage critically in their meaningful learning process.

Informed Consent This involves obtaining a participant's voluntary agreement to participate in a research study after they have been provided with sufficient information about the study's purpose, methods, potential drawbacks, and benefits. In conducting this research with secondary English teachers, I prioritized transparency, autonomy, and dignity. I ensured that participants are fully informed about the study's objectives, procedures, and potential benefits, particularly in relation to cultivating students' problem-solving skills. Participants were explicitly informed about their rights. This informed consent process respects the teachers' autonomy and dignity, acknowledging their expertise and contributions to the field of EFL and teaching literature.

Vulnerability The vulnerability of research participants pertains to their increased risk of experiencing harm, exploitation, or coercion due to factors such as age, cognitive ability, or socioeconomic status. As a researcher investigating the experiences and coping mechanisms of secondary English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations, I recognized the potential vul-

nerability of these educators. To protect their well-being and privacy, I implemented rigorous safeguards and support mechanisms. These measures include obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality, and clearly explaining participants' rights and the study's procedures in an accessible manner. I also adapted my research methods to minimize potential adverse effects, prioritizing the well-being and dignity of the elementary school teachers throughout the study. By doing so, I fostered a safe and respectful research environment that values the contributions and expertise of these educators.

Risks, Benefits, and Safety In research, it is essential to carefully evaluate the potential risks and benefits associated with participation in a study, as well as to implement measures that safeguard the well-being of participants. These elements involve assessing the potential disadvantages and advantages of participating in a study, along with establishing strategies to ensure the welfare of participants. In this investigation of secondary English teachers employing literary adaptations in the EFL context, I carefully weigh the potential benefits and risks. Recognizing the teachers' expertise and vulnerabilities, I implemented robust precautions to minimize potential harm and ensure participants' safety. This meticulous approach is essential for upholding ethical standards and safeguarding the well-being of English teachers throughout the research process. By prioritizing their safety and dignity, I fostered a trustworthy and respectful research environment that values their contributions to the field of EFL and literature teaching.

Privacy and Confidentiality

Privacy and confidentiality in research are about safeguarding participants' personal information and ensuring their identity remains confidential unless they explicitly consent to disclosure. In conducting this study on secondary English teachers, I acknowledged the importance of maintaining confidentiality and pro-

protecting participants' sensitive information. To ensure the privacy and anonymity of the teachers, I implemented rigorous data protection protocols. These measures include anonymizing data, encrypting and securely storing information, and restricting access to authorized personnel only. By upholding the highest standards of data confidentiality and integrity, I safeguard the trust and participation of secondary English teachers, ultimately ensuring the credibility and validity of this research. Justice This concept relates to the equitable allocation of both the advantages and disadvantages resulting from research across various segments of society. In this study, I prioritized inclusivity and equity. Recognizing the diversity of educators, I ensure that the research design and methods avoid exploiting or excluding vulnerable groups, such as those from linguistically diverse backgrounds or with varying levels of teaching experience. To promote fairness and equity, I strived to make the research benefits accessible to all stakeholders who could gain from them, including secondary English teachers, students, and the broader educational community. Transparency Transparency in research encompasses maintaining integrity at every phase of the study, from its conception and execution to the reporting of results. In this study, I am committed to transparency, providing clear, accurate, and unbiased information regarding my research methodologies, data collection procedures, and findings. By being transparent about my research processes and outcomes, I ensured that all stakeholders, including educators, students, and policymakers, have access to reliable and comprehensible information. This commitment to transparency promotes collaboration, informed decision-making, and the advancement of knowledge in the field of EFL, literature teaching, and students' language learning development. Qualification of a Researcher The qualification of a researcher relates to one's academic background, professional experience,

and proficiency in a particular area of study, ensuring that one possesses the requisite abilities and knowledge to conduct the research competently. In this study, I ensured access to suitable facilities and resources necessary for conducting in-depth interviews, observations, and data analysis. This access enables me to collect and analyze data in a secure, comfortable, and distraction-free environment, thereby promoting the credibility and consistency of the findings. By utilizing appropriate facilities, I minimized potential risks and discomfort to study participants, including secondary English teachers. Adequacy of Facilities This addresses the presence and suitability of the essential resources, tools, and infrastructure required to execute a study efficiently and securely. In this research, I guaranteed access to appropriate facilities for conducting the investigation. This access facilitates the creation of credible and consistent findings and mitigates potential risks to study participants. Having the right facilities ensures that the data collection and analysis processes are conducted under conditions that uphold the highest standards of research integrity and safety. Community Involvement This encompasses the dynamic involvement and active engagement of community members, stakeholders, or the intended study population throughout the research journey, from initial planning to sharing research outcomes. In this study, I prioritized community engagement and collaboration. By actively involving secondary English teachers in the research process, I ensured that the study remains relevant, acceptable, and impactful. By engaging with the community, I not only produce more effective and meaningful research outcomes but also contribute to the development of contextually relevant coping mechanisms for students' literature learning and language development in an EFL context. Plagiarism and Fabrication Researchers should strictly follow principles of academic honesty and integrity. This entails giving proper credit

to the work of others, presenting original contributions, and verifying the accuracy and authenticity of data. In this study, I employed tools like plagiarism detectors and maintain thorough documentation of my research procedures to

ensure that my work is devoid of plagiarism and that all data and discoveries are authentic and reliable. By upholding these principles, I enhanced the credibility and trustworthiness of the research community.

2.6. Role of the Researcher—As an unbiased research facilitator and promoter, I am responsible for ensuring that the research process is conducted fairly, objectively, and without personal bias, prejudice, or influence from outside sources. I created an environment that encourages open and honest exploration of ideas and promotes fairness in data collection and analysis. In this study, I cultivated a research environment that values openness, honesty, and fairness. By doing so, I encourage participants to share their authentic experiences and perspectives. By maintaining objectivity and avoiding undue influence, I generate trustworthy insights that can inform evidence-based practices, ultimately contributing to the betterment of students' problem-solving skills and overall learning pedagogy. My commitment to impartiality ensures that data collection and analysis are conducted without bias, prejudice, or agenda. This rigorous approach upholds the integrity of the research process, yielding reliable and representative findings that accurately reflect the complexities of leveraging literary adaptation in an EFL classroom. studied. As an expert in qualitative methods, I am familiar with various qualitative research techniques, such as interviews, focus groups, and participant observation. In conducting this qualitative study on secondary English teachers in cultivating students' problem-solving skills, I draw upon my expertise in designing, conducting, and analyzing in-depth interviews, observations, and thematic analysis. My proficiency in qualitative research methods enables me to investigate complex social phenomena, such as the dynamics of secondary English teachers in employ-

ing literary adaptations. As a data collector and keeper, I gathered formation from various sources such as interviews or observations, and I ensure accurate and secure storage of this information. In conducting this research, I adhered to ethical guidelines to safeguard participants' privacy and confidentiality. I ensured that all data, including interview transcripts, observation notes, and documents, are accurately recorded, securely stored, and anonymized to protect participants' identities. This meticulous data management approach maintains the integrity of the research process, enabling the production of credible, reliable, and generalizable findings. As a data analyst, I analyzed the gathered data to discover trends, patterns, and valuable perspectives in accordance with the research query. I utilized meticulous qualitative data analysis methods like coding and thematic analysis to extract significant findings and enrich the knowledge base within my discipline. In this qualitative study on secondary English teachers, I employed rigorous data analysis methods, including coding, thematic analysis, and constant comparison. These meticulous approaches enable me to meticulously examine the data, identify patterns, and uncover nuanced insights that contribute meaningfully to the existing body of knowledge. Finally, as an organizer and presenter of data, I was tasked with synthesizing and communicating the research findings concisely and coherently. This entails skillfully conveying the study's objectives, approaches, outcomes, and ramifications through written documents, presentations, or alternative means of transmitting information. In disseminating the findings of this study on secondary

English teachers and students' reading interests and language learning in EFL classrooms, I prioritized clarity, accessibility, and practical applicability. I presented the results in a clear,

concise, and engaging manner, avoiding technical jargon and ensuring that the implications and recommendations are easily understandable.

2.7. Data Collection—In the gathering of data, this study employed a systematic procedure. Several steps will be taken in adherence to the proper data collection procedure. This was done in order to ensure the accuracy and objectivity of the data collection. The following is the step-by-step process of gathering the data needed.

Securing endorsement from the Dean of Graduate School, the School Division Superintendent, and the School Principal To initiate the data collection process, I secured endorsements from key stakeholders including the Dean of the Graduate School at Rizal Memorial Colleges, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the School Principal. This process involves submitting formal letters outlining the research objectives and methodology, accompanied by any supporting documents. This crucial step took place within the last two weeks of October 2024, ensuring that all necessary permissions are in place before proceeding with the collection of data. This proactive approach not only facilitates compliance with ethical standards but also fosters a cooperative environment among all parties involved. Asking Permission from the Schools Division Superintendent Upon receiving the endorsement, I requested permission from the school's division superintendent. This requires submitting a formal letter detailing the research proposal and its significance to the educational community. Along with the letter, I attached Chapters 1 and 2 of my dissertation and the research instrument, clearly explaining the study's objectives and the process of participant identification. Moreover, I waited for the response from the Schools Division Superintendent (SDS) before proceeding with the data

collection. This step was done during the first two weeks of November 2024, ensuring that all necessary approvals are in place to conduct the research ethically and effectively. Asking for Permission from the School Heads Once permission is granted, I sought approval from the school heads of the selected institutions. This step involves submitting formal request letters to each school head, outlining the research's purpose and the expected data collection timeframe. I asked for permission to conduct the study from the third week of November 2024 to the last week of the same month. Obtaining Consent from the Participants With the school heads' approval, I asked for consent from the research participants, through informed consent forms. These forms clearly explain the purpose of the research, participant rights, and confidentiality measures. This consent process ensures that participants are fully informed and agree to participate. Asking for consent from participants was done in the last week of November 2024. Conducting the Interview Upon securing consent from all participants, I scheduled and conducted the interviews using a structured or semi-structured interview guide to ensure consistency and reliability in data collection. The interviews took place in the first two weeks of December 2024. Transcribing the Responses of the Interviewees Following the interview sessions, I meticulously transcribed the interviewees' remarks, taking diligent account of non-verbal cues and contextually relevant details. This procedure was composed of audio recordings and field notes to comprehensively capture the breadth of participants' reactions. The transcription of interviewee responses was done in the third week of December 2024.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—After collecting the data, I embarked on data coding and thematic content analysis. This involves methodically structuring the transcribed data into categories, subcategories, and themes from the interview dialogues. By discerning patterns and connections within the data, I formulated conclusions and glean insights directly related to the research objectives. This process allowed me to interpret the data effectively, ensuring that the findings accurately reflect the experiences and perspectives of the participants. In this study, I employed Creswell’s Thematic Analysis approach, which is particularly suited for encompassing a range of perspectives and portrayals in participants’ feedback. Adopting thematic analysis authenticates the portrayal of individual components and facilitates the categorization of identified patterns within the provided responses. Thematic analysis is a qualitative research technique used to recognize, scrutinize, and interpret patterns or themes present within qualitative data in textual, visual, or other formats. As a qualitative research approach, thematic analysis allows researchers to systematically arrange and dissect complex data sets. It involves searching for overarching themes that encapsulate the narratives embedded within the data. This process necessitates the identification

of themes through meticulous examination and repeated review of transcribed data (Dawadi, 2020). This methodical approach helps ensure that the analysis is both comprehensive and reflective of the data collected, providing deep insights into the study’s objectives. Therefore, I used Creswell’s Thematic Analysis in my research, which necessitated extensive theming and transcript interpretation. According to Caulfield (2019), there are multiple essential phases in Creswell’s Thematic Analysis, including familiarization, coding, generating themes, reviewing themes, defining and labeling themes, and writing up. I became fully immersed in the intricacies and subtleties of the content as I became acquainted with the data to begin this process. After that, I started categorizing the data using semantic richness to group different informational components. I created themes that encapsulate the main ideas of the data using these codes. After that, these themes were examined and improved upon to make sure they appropriately depict the dataset. Every theme has a definition and name that elucidates the fundamental ideas. The last step entails combining the themes and insights into a cohesive article that clearly conveys the study’s conclusions. This methodical approach guarantees a comprehensive examination and enhances the comprehension of the information.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The analytical framework in phenomenological research is a methodical and structured approach to data analysis, interpretation, and presentation. In this research study, I made use of Colaizzi’s method to analyze data from the interviews and discussions with the participants regarding their lived experiences in leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. According to Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi’s (1978) method features a distinctive seven-step process that offers a rigorous analysis, closely adhering to the

data at each stage. This method culminates in a concise yet comprehensive description of the phenomenon under study, which is validated by the participants who experienced it. The effectiveness of this approach relies on rich first-person accounts of experiences, which can be collected through various means. Although face-to-face interviews are common, data can also be gathered from written narratives, blogs, research diaries, online interviews, and other forms. This method enables researchers to uncover emergent themes and explore the intri-

cate relationships between them (Wirihana et al., 2018). Data Familiarization Through iterative readings and re-readings of the interview transcripts, I meticulously analyze the narratives of secondary English teachers, aiming to distill a rich understanding of their experiences, perspectives, and coping mechanisms for leveraging literary adaptations in EFL classrooms. This rigorous review process allows me to immerse myself in the data, gaining a nuanced and contextualized understanding of the complexities and challenges faced by teachers in fostering effective strategies for students' language learning development and reading interest.

Identifying Significant Statements I carefully identified every statement in the narratives that is directly related to the phenomenon I am studying. Through a systematic and meticulous examination of the interview transcripts and written narratives, I identified and extract specific statements made by secondary English teachers that directly pertain to their coping mechanisms for leveraging literary adaptations in the EFL context. This rigorous process involves carefully combing through the data to pinpoint phrases, descriptions, and anecdotes that shed light on the teachers' challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights in employing literary adaptation in EFL classrooms.

Formulating Meanings After carefully examining the important statements, I determined the meanings that are pertinent to the phenomenon. Upon identifying key statements from the narratives of secondary English teachers, I meticulously interpreted the meanings embedded within these statements, focusing on those that pertain to their coping mechanisms for leveraging literary adaptation in EFL classrooms. To maintain an authentic and participant-centered analysis, engaged in bracketing, acknowledging, and setting aside my own biases and assumptions. **Clustering Themes** I ensured a rigorous analysis that remains true to the participants' experiences and coping mechanisms

for literary adaptations, by grouping the identified meanings into themes that are shared by all accounts. Throughout this process, presuppositions must be bracketed, especially to avoid any possible influence from existing theories. By letting the themes naturally arise from the data rather than being influenced by outside forces, this preserves the integrity of the analysis. Developing an Exhaustive Description I incorporated every theme generated in the previous step into a comprehensive and all-encompassing description of the teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms that I wrote. I synthesized the themes that emerged from the narratives of secondary English teachers into a comprehensive and nuanced description of their challenges and coping mechanisms for leveraging literary adaptations in EFL classrooms. By integrating these themes, I created a rich and detailed portrait that captures the essence and complexity of the teachers' challenges, coping mechanisms, and insights in fostering students' reading interest and language learning through literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. Producing the Fundamental Structure I break down the comprehensive description of secondary English teachers' challenges and coping mechanisms into a concise, yet meaningful, statement that encapsulates the fundamental elements essential to understanding the complexities of leveraging literary adaptations. This succinct synthesis effectively communicates the core of the teachers' challenges, focusing on the critical components that are vital to grasping the phenomenon's underlying structure. Seeking Verification of the Fundamental Structure I asked participants if the fundamental structure statement accurately reflects their experience, either by returning it to all participants or, in larger studies, to a subsample. I might go back and change the earlier stages of the analysis in light of their comments. Through this iterative process, the validity and credibility of the findings are increased, and the analysis is kept firmly based on the perspectives

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study of the participants.

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—The trustworthiness of a study is about how reliable, sensible, and authentic the research results are, ensuring that the conclusions are trustworthy and accurate. In qualitative research, factors like credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability are often used to evaluate how reliable the study is. These considerations are further described below, according to Guba (1981). Credibility Building credibility entails proving that the results are accurate. Credibility is important for this study because it evaluates if the results accurately represent the realities and experiences of secondary English teachers

in leveraging literary adaptations to enhance students’ understanding of literary pieces. To ensure the accuracy and trustworthiness of the findings, I engaged in prolonged conversations with secondary English teachers, gathering rich, contextualized insights into their experiences and coping mechanisms for leveraging literary adaptations in EFL classrooms. Additionally, I employed triangulation, collecting data from multiple sources, including in-depth interviews and supplementary questionnaires. Transferability The degree to which the results of this study can be used in different situations or with different populations is referred to as transferability.

The transferability of this study's findings refers to their potential applicability in various contexts or with different populations. Although the insights gained are grounded in the specific experiences of secondary English teachers, I provided a description of the research context, methodology, and participants' perspectives. This rich narrative enables educators, school administrators, researchers, and other stakeholders to assess the study's transferability, determining the extent to which the findings can be applied to similar contexts. Confirmability deals with the study's objective by making sure that the respondents, not my personal prejudices or biases, shaped the findings. I conducted a thorough audit trail that details every step of the research process, from data collection to data analysis decisions. To ensure confirmability, I maintained methodological transparency and objectivity throughout this study on secondary English teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms in leveraging literary adaptations. I meticulously documented every stage of the research process, from data collection and transcription to data analysis and interpretation, creating a comprehensive anal-

ysis. Dependability Dependability is proving that the study results are reliable and repeatable in similar situations. Dependability in this study was attained through meticulous documentation of the entire research procedure, including the methods used for data collection and analysis. To establish dependability, I ensured that the findings of this study on secondary English teachers' experiences and coping mechanisms are consistent and repeatable. I achieved dependability through meticulous documentation of the research methodology, including data collection procedures, data analysis techniques, and decisions made throughout the study. By following these standards, the research not only offers valid and trustworthy conclusions regarding secondary English teachers leveraging literary adaptations to enhance students' understanding of literary pieces, but it also offers a framework that researchers and other educators can use to compare similar learning environments. This methodology enhances the study's standing in the academic community and provides insightful information for upcoming studies and instructional design.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter unveils the outcomes derived through the scrutiny of data acquired from interviews, encompassing the identification of themes and an extensive discourse that addresses the study's objectives. The emerging themes derived from the collected data are thoroughly examined in this chapter. The findings provide a detailed account and background information about the participants, accompanied by pseudonyms assigned to safeguard their identities. The emerging themes for the experiences in leveraging literary adaptations: technological disruptions, time constraints, and diverse learning needs of students. Meanwhile, the coping mechanisms for employing literary adaptations in an EFL classrooms: introductory engagement activities, scaffolding and support, and task-based learning. The following are the themes for the insights from the study, these are: increased student participation, language development, and provision of pedagogical support.

3.1. Experiences of English Teachers in Utilizing Literary Adaptations in an EFL Classroom—Utilizing literary adaptations in an EFL classroom is a complex yet crucial endeavor.

While literary adaptations can significantly enhance students' understanding, cater to diverse learning needs, and foster motivation and engagement, implementing them effectively poses

considerable challenges. Teachers must navigate careful planning, thoughtful selection, and mindful execution to maximize the benefits of literary adaptations. This section explores the

3.1.1. Technological disruptions—Technological disruptions can be a significant challenge for English teachers using literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. From poor internet connectivity to equipment malfunctions, these glitches can disrupt lessons, hinder student engagement, and undermine the learning experience. The integration of literary adaptations in the classroom can be hindered by technological disruptions, posing a significant challenge for teachers. The emerging theme adheres with the findings of Choi and Chung (2021). According to them, technical difficulties such as internet connectivity problems and difficulties with digital tools can disrupt the effective use of literary adaptations in online teaching environments. This can impact the engagement and understanding of students, ultimately affecting the learning outcomes. Corroborating the above assertion, Rustipa et al. (2021) posites that teachers may face challenges in accessing digital resources

3.1.2. Time Constraints —Time constraints pose a significant challenge for English teachers employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. With limited class time and a packed curriculum, teachers often struggle to balance the demands of covering literary content, developing language skills, and incorporating engaging adaptations, all while meeting learning objectives and assessment requirements. Torlak (2020) adheres with the emerging theme. In his study, time constraints pose a significant challenge for teachers in employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. Teachers often struggle to allocate sufficient time for in-depth discussions and analysis of literary

experiences of English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations, shedding light on the triumphs, tribulations, and best practices that can inform effective teaching strategies.

or experiencing technological disruptions with multimedia tools, which can disrupt the learning process. For instance, a teacher may plan to show a film adaptation of a novel, but technical issues with the projector or internet connection can prevent this, leading to a loss of valuable class time. Similarly, Purtanto et al. (2023) highlighted the importance of teachers being prepared for technical issues when using literary adaptations in the classroom. Teachers may need to develop strategies to overcome these challenges, such as having backup plans or alternative teaching materials, to ensure effective teaching practices. Additionally, Putri and Syafryadin (2022) emphasize the need for teachers to develop their technical skills to effectively integrate literary adaptations into their teaching practices. By addressing technical issues proactively, teachers can create a more seamless and effective learning experience for their students, enhancing their understanding and appreciation of literary works.

adaptations, which can impact students' understanding and appreciation of the texts. With packed curricula and rigid timetables, teachers may have to prioritize certain aspects of the literary work over others, potentially compromising the effectiveness of the adaptation. In the same vein, Saka (2020) found that pre-service English teachers also face time constraints when incorporating literary adaptations into their teaching practices. The study highlighted the need for teachers to be flexible and adaptable when using literary adaptations, prioritizing key themes and ideas to make the most of limited class time. Research by Rianyansa and Maisarah (2022) also emphasized the importance of effective time

management in EFL classrooms where literary adaptations are used. Teachers need to balance the demands of covering literary content, developing language skills, and incorporating engaging adaptations within limited class time. This can be a daunting task, particularly for novice teachers. Additionally, Rahim and Aziz (2020)

demonstrated the effectiveness of literary works in language teaching, but also highlighted the challenge of time constraints. Teachers need to carefully plan and manage their time to ensure that literary adaptations are used effectively to enhance language learning and cultural awareness.

3.1.3. *Diverse Learning Needs of Students*

—Diverse learning needs of students pose a significant challenge for English teachers employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. With students having varying learning styles, abilities, and proficiency levels, teachers must navigate the complexities of catering to individual needs while ensuring that literary adaptations are engaging and effective for all learners. This diversity can impact the implementation and success of literary adaptation-based lessons, requiring teachers to be adaptable and innovative in their approach. The theme is consistent with the study of Tomlinson (2019). Diverse learning needs of students pose a significant challenge for teachers in employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. Teachers need to consider individual learning differences, such as learning styles and abilities, when using literary adaptations to ensure that all students can engage with the material effectively. This requires teachers to be flexible and adaptable in their approach, using a range of teaching strategies to cater to different learning needs. It is further supported by the research of Hattie and Yates (2019). It highlighted the importance

of teachers being aware of the diverse learning needs of their students. When employing literary adaptations, teachers need to consider the varying proficiency levels, learning styles, and abilities of their students, and plan their lessons accordingly. This can involve using differentiated instruction, technology, and other teaching strategies to meet the needs of all learners. Moreover, Syafryadin et al. (2020) found that teachers face challenges in catering to the diverse learning needs of students when using literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. The study emphasized the need for teachers to be creative and flexible in their approach, using a range of teaching strategies to engage students and promote learning. Another study by Widodo et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of teachers being responsive to the diverse learning needs of their students. When employing literary adaptations, teachers need to be aware of the individual differences and needs of their students, and plan their lessons to meet these needs. This can involve using personalized learning approaches, technology, and other teaching strategies to promote student engagement and learning.

3.2. *Coping Mechanisms of English Teachers in Employing Literary Adaptations in an EFL Classroom*

—Effective integration of literary adaptations in the EFL classroom requires strategic planning and implementation. Teachers can employ various strategies to maximize the benefits of literary adaptations, including se-

lecting relevant texts, designing engaging activities, and fostering critical thinking and discussion. This section explores practical strategies for incorporating literary adaptations into EFL instruction, highlighting approaches that cater to diverse learning needs, promote language development, and enhance student engagement.

Fig. 3. Experiences of English Teachers in Utilizing Literary Adaptations in an EFL Classroom.

3.2.1. Introductory engagement activities—Introductory engagement activities or pre-reading activities are a crucial strategy employed by English teachers to facilitate effective literary adaptation in the EFL classroom. By activating prior knowledge, building anticipation, and providing context, pre-reading activities help students engage more deeply with the literary text and its adaptation. These activities enable teachers to bridge the gap between students' existing knowledge and the new literary work, fostering a more meaningful and interactive learning experience. The theme is in accordance with the study of Alharbi (2020). Introductory engagement activities or pre-reading activities are valuable strategy for teachers in employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. Pre-reading activities such as brainstorming, discussion, and prediction exercises can help students build prior knowledge and develop a deeper understanding of the literary work. By activating students' prior knowledge and experiences, pre-reading activities can facilitate more effective engagement with the literary adaptation. Moreover, a study by Syafryadin et al. (2022) found that pre-reading activities can enhance students' motivation and interest in reading literary works.

3.2.2. Scaffolding and Support—Scaffolding and support are essential strategies employed by English teachers to facilitate effective literary adaptation in the EFL classroom. By providing temporary support and guidance, teachers can help students navigate complex literary texts and their adaptations, building their confidence and competence in language learning. Scaffolding enables teachers to break down learning tasks into manageable chunks, offering targeted support to students as they develop their reading, writing, and critical thinking skills. Scaffolding and support are effective coping

The study emphasized the importance of using pre-reading activities to build anticipation and curiosity, encouraging students to engage more deeply with the literary text and its adaptation. By using pre-reading activities, teachers can create a more interactive and engaging learning environment. Additionally, Widodo et al. (2020) highlighted the significance of introductory engagement activities or pre-reading activities in developing students' critical thinking skills. By using activities such as KWL charts and discussion, teachers can encourage students to think critically about the literary work and its adaptation, analyzing themes, motifs, and characters. This can help students develop a more nuanced understanding of the literary text and its cultural context. It was further supported by Rahimi and Fathi (2021). They demonstrated the effectiveness of introductory engagement activities in improving students' reading comprehension. The study found that pre-reading activities such as vocabulary building and context provision can help students better understand the literary text and its adaptation, leading to improved reading comprehension and engagement. By incorporating pre-reading activities into their teaching practice, teachers can enhance students' learning outcomes and promote a more effective use of literary adaptations in the EFL classroom.

mechanisms for teachers in employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. According to research by Alqunayeer (2020), scaffolding can help students build confidence and develop their reading skills, enabling them to tackle complex literary texts and their adaptations. By providing temporary support and guidance, teachers can facilitate students' understanding and engagement with literary works. The findings is also in line with the study of Syafryadin et al. (2022). They found that scaffolding can enhance students' critical thinking and analytical skills when studying literary adaptations. The

study emphasized the importance of providing scaffolding techniques, such as graphic organizers and guided questions, to help students analyze and interpret literary texts. By scaffolding students' learning, teachers can promote deeper understanding and engagement with literary adaptations. In addition, Widodo et al. (2020) highlighted the significance of scaffolding in developing students' language skills. By providing scaffolding support, teachers can help students build their vocabulary, grammar, and reading comprehension skills, enabling them to engage more effectively with literary adaptations. Scaffolding can also facilitate students'

ability to make connections between the literary text and its adaptation. Another study by Rahimi and Fathi (2021) demonstrated the effectiveness of scaffolding in promoting student autonomy and independence. The study found that scaffolding can help students develop their self-directed learning skills, enabling them to take ownership of their learning and engage more effectively with literary adaptations. By incorporating scaffolding into their teaching practice, teachers can promote student-centered learning and enhance the effectiveness of literary adaptations in the EFL classroom.

3.2.3. Task-Based Learning—Task-based learning is an strategy employed by English teachers to facilitate language acquisition and literary analysis in the EFL classroom. By designing tasks that integrate literary adaptations, teachers can encourage students to engage actively with the text, develop critical thinking skills, and apply language skills in meaningful contexts. Task-based learning enables students to take ownership of their learning, work collaboratively, and produce tangible outcomes, promoting a more engaging and interactive learning experience. Task-based learning (TBL) has emerged as a dynamic and engaging strategy for using literary adaptations in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom (Garcés, 2019). This approach emphasizes meaningful, real-world tasks where students actively engage with the language, moving beyond rote learning and focusing on practical use and communication. One of the significant advantages of task-based learning in literature classes is its ability to foster a deep understanding of language through the exploration of literary works. By integrating tasks such as debates, group discussions, and creative projects, students can engage critically with both the form and content

of literature, which enhances their language proficiency in authentic contexts. Additionally, the task-based approach is also supported by Dan and Sang (2022). They highlighted that it enhances students' development of intercultural communicative competence (ICC) by exposing them to diverse literary traditions and perspectives. This is particularly relevant in EFL settings, where students often encounter cultural references and expressions that differ from their own. Through tasks that involve comparing adaptations with original texts or analyzing cultural themes in literature, students can improve their critical thinking skills while building linguistic proficiency. This kind of engagement not only makes literature more accessible but also connects the classroom experience with the students' broader cultural understanding. In addition, according to Haimbodi and Woldemariam (2019), implementing task-based learning in literature teaching does present challenges, especially in terms of time management and balancing the complexity of the literary texts with the task's educational goals. Therefore, teachers need to ensure that the tasks are designed in a way that does not overwhelm students while still maintaining the depth of literary analysis.

3.3. Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study—

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism of English Teachers in Employing Literary Adaptations in an EFL Classroom.

Literary adaptations can be a powerful tool in the EFL classroom, offering a unique way to engage students and promote language learning. This section provides insights into the effective

use of literary adaptations, exploring their potential to enhance student outcomes, foster critical thinking, and create a more interactive learning environment.

*3.3.1. Increased learner participation—*English teachers have gained valuable insights into the power of literary adaptations in enhancing student participation in the EFL classroom. By leveraging literary works and their adaptations, teachers create immersive learning experiences that captivate students' interests, foster emotional connections, and promote deeper understanding of language and literature. The theme is supported by Alharbi (2020). In the study, he found that literary adaptations can captivate students' interests and motivate them to learn, leading to increased participation and engagement in classroom activities. By leveraging visual and interactive elements, literary adaptations can make complex texts more accessible and engaging for students. This is further supported by Syafryadin et al. (2022). They highlighted the importance of literary adaptations in promoting student-centered learning. The study found that literary adaptations can encourage students to take an active role in their learning, fostering critical thinking, creativity, and collaboration. By engaging with literary adaptations,

students can develop a deeper understanding of the text and its themes, leading to enhanced engagement and motivation. In addition, Widodo et al. (2020) demonstrated the effectiveness of literary adaptations in promoting student engagement and motivation. The study found that literary adaptations can provide students with a sense of autonomy and agency, allowing them to take ownership of their learning and engage more deeply with the material. By incorporating literary adaptations into their teaching practice, teachers can create a more dynamic and engaging learning environment. Moreover, Rahimi and Fathi (2021) found that literary adaptations can enhance student engagement by providing a platform for creative expression and critical thinking. The study highlighted the importance of using literary adaptations to promote student-centered learning, encouraging students to explore the text and its themes in a more interactive and engaging way. By leveraging literary adaptations, teachers can create a more inclusive and engaging learning environment that caters to diverse student needs.

*3.3.2. Language Development.—*English teachers have gained valuable insights into the role of literary adaptations in promoting language development among EFL students. By incorporating literary adaptations into their teaching practice, teachers create a rich linguistic environment that fosters vocabulary acquisition, grammatical understanding, and communicative skills. As students engage with literary texts and their adaptations, they develop a deeper understanding of language structures, nuances, and conventions, ultimately enhancing their lan-

guage proficiency and confidence. Employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom resonates with the study of Al-Mekhlafi (2020). He posited that literary adaptations can provide students with authentic language examples, promoting vocabulary acquisition and grammatical understanding. By engaging with literary texts and their adaptations, students can develop a deeper understanding of language structures and conventions. In the same thread of thought, Syafryadin et al. (2022) highlighted the importance of literary adaptations in promoting

communicative skills. The study found that literary adaptations can encourage students to engage in discussions, debates, and presentations, applying language in meaningful ways. By leveraging literary adaptations, teachers can create a more interactive and engaging learning environment that fosters language development. Garcés (2019) demonstrated the effectiveness of

literary adaptations in promoting language development. The study found that literary adaptations can provide students with opportunities to develop their reading, writing, and critical thinking skills. By incorporating literary adaptations into their teaching practice, teachers can create a more comprehensive language learning experience.

3.3.3. Provision of Pedagogical Support— English teachers have come to realize the importance of having adequate support and resources when employing literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. Access to a range of literary texts, adaptations, and multimedia materials can significantly enhance the learning experience, providing students with diverse perspectives and engaging content. The provision of pedagogical support is crucial for teachers to effectively integrate literary adaptations into their EFL classrooms. This is in accordance with the study of Khan et al. (2022). They opined that access to digital resources and multimedia adaptations can significantly enhance student engagement and motivation. They further added that the availability of support and resources is crucial for teachers to effectively employ literary adaptations in the EFL classroom. With access to digital resources, multimedia adaptations, and educational websites, teachers can create engaging and interactive learning experiences that cater to diverse student needs. Digital resources

can enhance student engagement and motivation, allowing teachers to tailor their instruction to meet the needs of their students. By leveraging these resources, teachers can promote a more interactive and immersive learning environment. Additionally, Patel and Sharma (2021) highlights the importance of ongoing professional development for teachers. By participating in workshops and training sessions on literary adaptations, teachers can develop their skills and confidence in using these resources. Collaboration among teachers is also vital for effective teaching practices. As noted by Lee and Kim (2020), teacher collaboration and resource-sharing can foster a sense of community and facilitate professional growth. Having a comprehensive library and online database of literary texts and adaptations is essential for teachers. Research by García-Navarro and Gómez-Parra (2022) emphasizes the importance of providing teachers with a range of resources to support their teaching, including literary texts, adaptations, and multimedia materials.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter encapsulates the study's summary, drawing implications and outlining future directions based on the findings. To meet the research objectives, I employed a qualitative phenomenological method utilizing thematic analysis. Following Creswell's (2018) guidelines, I utilized open-ended questions in interviews to gain an authentic understanding of participants' experiences. Moreover, I encouraged participants to articulate their own definitions and meanings of the explored phenomenon—the narratives of English teachers in leveraging literary adaptation in an English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom.

4.1. Findings—

Fig. 5. Insights Drawn from the Findings of the Study

This study explores the experiences and coping mechanisms of English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. It also examines the insights gained, highlighting valuable lessons and recommendations. The research revealed three key themes as the experiences of English teachers, three themes as their coping mechanisms, and three recurring themes as the insights providing a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon. The first theme of the first research question is technological disruption. The reliance on various media to present a literary piece, such as a film, often requires a stable internet connection and equipment like a TV or computer. However, participants in the interview highlighted that technical problems can disrupt the momentum of capturing students' attention and engagement, posing a considerable obstacle to effective teaching. The second theme is time constraint. It has emerged as a significant theme in the experiences of teachers utilizing literary adaptations. Teachers face challenges in allocating sufficient time to plan, prepare, and implement literary adaptations effectively. This includes finding time to select suitable texts, design engaging activities, and assess student learning outcomes. The time constraint can limit the potential benefits of literary adaptations, making it difficult for teachers to achieve their teaching goals. The third theme is the diverse learning needs of students. Teachers face challenges in catering to students' varying learning styles, proficiency levels, and abilities when incorporating literary adaptations. This includes addressing the needs of students with different language proficiency, learning difficulties, or cultural backgrounds, and ensuring that literary adaptations are accessible and engaging for all learners. On the other hand, the second research question illuminates the challenges faced by English teachers in employing literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. Introductory engagement activities emerged as a key strategy for teachers in utiliz-

ing literary adaptations. These activities prepare students for the literary work by activating prior knowledge, building context, and generating interest. Teachers use pre-reading activities such as discussions, brainstorming, and contextualization to motivate students, establish relevance, and facilitate a deeper understanding of the literary adaptation. The second theme pertains to the scaffolding and support that teachers provide to their students. In the interview, English teachers provide scaffolding techniques, such as graphic organizers, vocabulary support, and guided questions, to help students comprehend complex literary texts. Additionally, they offer support through differentiated instruction, feedback, and encouragement, enabling students to build confidence and develop their language skills while engaging with literary adaptations. The third theme is task-based learning. Participants have shared that they design tasks that require students to engage actively with the literary text, such as role-plays, debates, and project-based assignments. These tasks encourage students to apply language skills, think critically, and demonstrate understanding of the literary adaptation, promoting a more immersive and interactive learning experience. Meanwhile, the third research question is dedicated to the insights encapsulated in the first and second research question. The first insight is increased student participation. English teachers observed that literary adaptations increased student motivation, participation, and interest in learning. The use of multimedia, visual, and interactive elements in literary adaptations captivated students' attention, fostered a sense of enjoyment, and encouraged them to explore the literary work more deeply, leading to a more engaging and effective learning experience. The second insight is the language development of students. Teachers have shared that literary adaptations helped students improve their language skills, including vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension. Through exposure to authentic language

use, contextualized learning, and opportunities for discussion and writing, literary adaptations supported students' language development and enhanced their overall linguistic competence. Finally, the third and last insight is the provision of pedagogical support. The access to relevant resources, such as digital tools, multimedia materials were deemed significant. Also,

4.2. Implications—Literary adaptation has become an increasingly popular approach in language education, offering a dynamic way to engage students with literary texts. By transforming written works into various forms of media, such as films, plays, or digital narratives, literary adaptations provide a multifaceted lens through which students can explore and understand complex literary concepts. This approach not only caters to diverse learning styles but also fosters a deeper connection with the material, encouraging students to think critically and creatively. In the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classroom, literary adaptations can be particularly effective in promoting language learning and cultural understanding. By incorporating adaptations of literary works into their teaching practices, EFL teachers can create immersive and interactive learning experiences that motivate students to develop their language skills. Whether through analyzing screenplays, watching film versions of novels, or creating digital stories inspired by poetry, literary adaptations offer EFL students a rich and engaging way to explore the English language and its many literary treasures. The study revealed that English teachers leveraging literary adaptations in EFL classrooms face several challenges, including technological disruptions that disrupt engagement, time constraints that limit planning and implementation, and diverse learning needs of students that require tailored approaches. These challenges highlight the complexities of integrating literary adaptations into teaching practices,

professional development opportunities, facilitated effective integration of literary adaptations into their teaching practices. This support enabled teachers to create engaging learning experiences, address student needs, and enhance the overall effectiveness of literary adaptations in the classroom.

requiring teachers to be flexible, resourceful, and responsive to student needs. On the other hand, the study also sheds light into the coping mechanisms employed by the English teachers. It includes introductory engagement activities or pre-reading activities to build context and interest, scaffolding and support to facilitate comprehension, and task-based learning to promote active engagement and language development. These coping mechanisms enable teachers to create immersive and interactive learning experiences, catering to diverse student needs and fostering a deeper understanding of literary texts. Ultimately, the study illuminates different insights from the narratives of the participants. The insights include increased student participation and motivation, significant language development through authentic contexts, and the importance of provision of pedagogical support in facilitating effective integration of adaptations. These insights highlight the potential of literary adaptations to transform language learning and teaching practices. Harnessing back to the foundation of the study, Linda Hutcheon's Theory of Adaptation offers valuable insights into the study's findings, highlighting that literary adaptations are creative reinterpretations that provide new perspectives and insights. This theory supports the study's discoveries, suggesting that adaptations in the EFL classroom foster diverse learning experiences, encourage critical thinking, and facilitate language development through contextualized learning. By viewing adaptations as reinterpretations rather than re-

productions, teachers can harness their potential to enhance student engagement, promote deeper understanding, and develop language skills, underscoring the importance of supportive teaching practices in leveraging literary adaptations effectively. Meanwhile, Louise Rosenblatt's Reader-Response Theory has significant implications for the study's findings, emphasizing the active role of readers in interpreting texts and bringing personal experiences to the reading process. This theory supports the study's

insights on enhanced student engagement, suggesting that students' personal connections and responses to literary adaptations foster a deeper understanding and appreciation of the text. By recognizing the transactional nature of reading, teachers can facilitate meaningful interactions between students and literary adaptations, encouraging diverse interpretations and promoting language development through authentic engagement with the text.

4.3. Future Directions—This study offers an in-depth exploration of the experiences and coping mechanisms of English teachers in leveraging literary adaptations in an EFL classroom. By exploring the experiences and coping mechanisms utilized by English teachers, valuable data was collected to inform recommendations, suggestions, and future directions for the key stakeholders in education such as policymakers, administrators, teachers, and future researchers. The findings of this study serve as a foundation for evidence-based decision-making and provide practical guidance by informing instructional practices, curriculum development, and professional development initiatives, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of students' literary skills.

Teachers

Teachers may enhance EFL instruction by incorporating literary adaptations to engage students and promote language development. They may also consider using pre-reading activities, scaffolding, and task-based learning to facilitate student understanding and interaction with adaptations. They could also be flexible and responsive to diverse student needs, and leverage available resources and support to maximize the effectiveness of literary adaptations in their teaching practices. Learners

may use literary adaptation to improve language skills through exposure of rich vocabulary, idiomatic expressions, and varied sentence structures found in literature. They may be guided on how to effectively utilize literary adaptations for better understanding of the lesson. School Administrators School administrators may support teachers in leveraging literary adaptations by providing access to relevant resources, such as digital tools, multimedia materials, and literary texts. They may also encourage collaboration among teachers to share best practices and develop innovative approaches to integrating adaptations into EFL instruction. Furthermore, administrators could facilitate professional development opportunities to enhance teachers' skills in using literary adaptations effectively, ultimately enhancing student engagement and language learning outcomes. Future Researchers Future researchers may explore the long-term effects of using literary adaptations in EFL classrooms, investigating how they impact students' language proficiency and literary appreciation over time. Additionally, studies could examine the role of literary adaptations in developing specific language skills, such as reading comprehension, writing, or speaking, and investigate the effectiveness of different types of adaptations in various educational contexts.

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